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Exploring the Role of Gender in Pronunciation Learning Strategies among Young CLIL and Non-CLIL Learners

Abstract

Gender and learning context have been considered two variables affecting both the frequency and the selection of strategies in self-regulated language learning. However, the role of gender in CLIL and non-CLIL contexts with respect to pronunciation learning strategies has not yet been explored. The present study compares pronunciation learning strategies and tactics used by boys and girls aged 7-10 in CLIL and non-CLIL learning contexts. A total of 327 primary education pupils (163 boys and 164 girls) completed a 27-item questionnaire with a 5-point Likert scale. The results reveal no significant differences in overall, cognitive, memory, metacognitive, affective or social strategies in either context. A closer examination of individual tactics revealed few gender differences. None were observed among CLIL learners, whereas non-CLIL boys reported higher use than girls of three tactics: recording their own voice, rewarding themselves for good pronunciation outcomes, and asking teachers to slow down or repeat. These findings differ from previous research with older learners, which has suggested gender differences in language learning strategy use. They also highlight the need for further research on how gender dynamics evolve in the use of strategies and tactics for pronunciation learning.

Keywords: pronunciation learning strategies, gender, CLIL, EFL, young learners

1. Introduction

Gender¹ has long been recognized as a significant factor in second and foreign language acquisition research. Numerous studies have explored gender differences across various dimensions of language learning, including motivation (Iwaniec, 2019), language anxiety (Dewaele & MacIntyre, 2014), pronunciation (Díaz-Campos, 2004), or learning strategies (Green & Oxford, 1995). Research in these domains frequently reports that female learners tend to be more motivated, experience higher levels of anxiety, attain more native-like pronunciation, and employ language learning strategies more frequently.

However, emerging research suggests that gender differences may be moderated by the learning context. For instance, studies conducted in CLIL contexts have reported no significant gender-based differences in the areas examined (Gallardo-del-Puerto & Blanco-Suárez, 2021; Heras & Lasagabaster, 2015; Nieto Moreno de Diezmas & Hill, 2019). The claim that CLIL contexts eliminate gender effects, however, has been contested. Some scholars argue that the absence of gender differences in CLIL is likewise observed in non-CLIL environments (Doiz et al., 2014; Martínez Agudo, 2022), while others maintain that girls outperform boys regardless of instructional context (Lasagabaster, 2008; Roquet et al., 2016).

Despite extensive investigation into language learning strategies (LLS), studies specifically examining their use in CLIL contexts remain scarce (Pawlak, 2021). Castellano-Risco (2019) provided evidence that CLIL learners use overall more vocabulary learning strategies and employ tactics that require deeper cognitive engagement. However, few studies have explored the intersection of CLIL, gender, and strategy use. Notably, those that have investigated this intersection report no significant gender-based differences in the use of general LLS (Milla & Gutierrez-Mangado, 2019) or compensatory strategies (Basterrechea et al., 2017), though these studies did not include non-CLIL samples for comparison. Consequently, it remains unclear whether non-CLIL environments exhibit a similar pattern.

The scarcity of studies is particularly evident in research on pronunciation learning strategies (PLS), an area that remains underexplored. To date, no study seems to have explicitly examined the interaction between instructional context (CLIL vs. non-CLIL) and gender in the use of PLS. The present study addresses this gap by providing empirical

¹ The study uses the term gender rather than sex to emphasize the influence of social roles and dynamics, as the research design does not allow attributing observed differences to biological factors. References to studies employing the term sex are also included, as they examine comparable aspects of learner variation, even if the terminology differs.

evidence on the self-reported use of PLS among boys and girls in both CLIL and non-CLIL contexts. Specifically, it investigates whether gender-based differences exist within each instructional setting. Additionally, the study adds evidence from young learners, thereby extending the existing body of research that has predominantly examined university-level populations.

2. Theoretical Framework

2.1. Language Learning Strategies (LLS)

LLS research investigates the deliberate actions learners use to facilitate acquisition. It has evolved from early descriptions of successful learners (Rubin, 1975) to broader examinations of mental, emotional, and social processes that support learning (Oxford, 1990). As Chamot (2005) notes, this line of research serves both theoretical and pedagogical purposes: understanding how learners acquire language and informing the instruction of strategies that lead to higher attainment.

Despite its contributions, LLS research has been marked by enduring debates, particularly around definitions and classifications (Oxford, 2017). Definitions vary depending on theoretical views concerning intentionality, consciousness, or context. The present study adopts a pedagogically aligned definition: LLS are “conscious, teachable, intentional, self-chosen, and self-regulated thoughts and actions for learning the target culture and language” (Oxford & Gkonou, 2018, p. 407). This definition refers to LLS as abstract and conceptual behaviors guiding learning processes. For the purposes of the present study, the term ‘tactic’ is used to designate specific and often observable actions through which learners put strategies into practice in concrete situations (Oxford, 2017, p. 15). In other words, strategies provide the overarching plan (e.g., monitoring one’s pronunciation), while tactics represent the practical steps that enact strategies (e.g., recording one’s voice to check for mistakes). The analysis in the present article, therefore, focuses on tactics as the measurable expressions of strategy use, which are subsequently grouped into broader categories according to their function for pronunciation acquisition and improvement.

A widely used LLS taxonomy proposed by Oxford (1990) distinguishes between direct strategies, which involve working directly with the target language, and indirect strategies, which support and manage the learning process without using the target language. Direct strategies include cognitive strategies (mental manipulation or application of language knowledge), memory strategies (storage and retrieval of linguistic

information), and compensation strategies (overcoming limitations in language proficiency). Indirect strategies include metacognitive strategies (planning, monitoring, and evaluating learning), affective strategies (managing emotions and motivation), and social strategies (interacting with others to enhance learning). More recent perspectives stress that strategy use is flexible and context-dependent. The same action may serve different functions depending on the task or the learner's goals, which suggests that established taxonomies should be viewed as useful organizing frameworks rather than fixed or exhaustive classifications (Oxford, 2017). Nevertheless, Oxford's (1990) framework remains one of the most established in the field and continues to be widely used. By offering a common set of categories, it allows results from different studies to be compared and generalized more easily. For this reason, the present article adopts Oxford's taxonomy as its organizing framework.

The most widely used instrument in LLS research remains the Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) (Oxford, 1990), developed in two versions: one for English speakers learning other languages and another for learners of English. The SILL provides an overall measure of learners' strategy use encompassing cognitive, metacognitive, social, affective, and compensatory strategies. However, the SILL is not skill-specific, and more recent research favors domain-specific approaches to capture how strategies are selected and applied. One such domain is pronunciation, where strategy research has received less emphasis compared to other language skills (Pawlak & Szyszka, 2018). Nevertheless, a body of research has emerged in recent decades examining how learners approach pronunciation development strategically, recognizing that deliberate strategy use can support pronunciation improvement.

2.2. Pronunciation Learning Strategies (PLS)

An early definition of PLS described them as “steps taken by students to enhance their own pronunciation learning” (Peterson, 2000, p. 7). Later, Pawlak (2010) provided a more detailed definition, describing PLS as “deliberate actions and thoughts that are consciously employed, often in a logical sequence, for learning and gaining greater control over the use of various aspects of pronunciation” (p. 191). As noted by Pawlak and Szyszka (2018), this definition highlights essential features such as purposefulness, conscious use, potential (un)observability, clustering, and relevance to both segmental and suprasegmental features. Pawlak's definition is the most relevant for the present

study, as pronunciation is understood here as “the production and reception of sounds of speech” (Dalton & Seidlhofer, 1994, p. 3).

Several studies have aimed to identify and categorize PLS. Peterson (2000), using diaries and interviews, identified 43 pronunciation learning tactics (PLT), later classified as PLS according to Oxford’s (1990) taxonomy. Pawlak (2010) proposed a taxonomy of PLS aligned with LLS categories (metacognitive, cognitive including memory, affective, and social), excluding compensatory strategies. He developed an instrument combining 60 Likert-scale items and open-ended questions, which was piloted with Polish English philology students who had prior pronunciation training.

Other studies have examined how frequently learners use different PLS categories. Całka (2011), using a pronunciation-adapted version of the SILL with Polish preservice EFL teachers, found that while learners employed all categories of strategies, they did not apply a wide variety of PLT. Memory and cognitive strategies were the most frequently used, while affective and social strategies were least used. Similarly, Szyszka (2014), through learner diaries and interviews, found that Polish EFL teacher trainees combined strategies into sequences, with cognitive and memory-based strategies being most common. Alghazo (2021) studied Jordanian EFL university students using classroom observations, a questionnaire, and interviews. In this study, cognitive strategies, such as repetition and formal practice, were most frequent, followed by social and metacognitive ones.

Some studies have investigated whether PLS use correlates with pronunciation proficiency in adult learners. Eckstein (2007) found in an ESL context in the US that PLS use positively correlated with comprehensibility, degree of native-like accent, fluency, and accuracy. Additionally, noticing errors, adjusting articulators, and seeking help were found to be positively associated with achievement, while repetition and volume modification were negatively associated. Baker Smemoe and Haslam (2013) analyzed an ESL sample in the US and an EFL sample in China and found a link between strategy use and comprehensibility, though weaker relationships with accuracy and fluency. In the Polish context, Rokoszewska (2012) found a weak correlation between PLS use and vowel production, and no correlation with vowel perception among Polish university students.

Instructional interventions have also been shown to influence learners’ use of PLS. Sardegna (2022), in a longitudinal study among adult learners in an ESL context in the

US, found that explicit PLS instruction significantly improved pronunciation outcomes. Pronunciation gains were maintained over time and were absent in the control group, whose learners neither received PLS instruction nor reported using these strategies. Jarosz (2021) found that brief, regular pronunciation instruction without explicit strategy training promoted PLS development among Polish secondary education students. However, the potential role of content-based instruction in the form of CLIL in shaping PLS use remains underexplored.

Individual differences have also been examined as potential factors influencing PLS use among adult learners. Szyszka (2017), in a Polish context, found that language anxiety negatively correlated with social strategy use. Regarding gender, Rokoszewska (2014) found no significant gender-based differences in PLS use among Polish university students enrolled in a pronunciation course. In contrast, Pawlak (2018) reported that, in a Polish context, female English majors used PLS more frequently and were more concerned with pronunciation accuracy than their male peers. The inconclusive results regarding gender and the scarcity of studies on this variable in PLS research highlight the need to consider findings from broader LLS literature, where gender has been more consistently examined as a factor influencing strategy use.

2.3. Gender and Strategy Use

Gender is frequently identified by scholars as a factor influencing LLS use (Oxford, 2017; Griffiths, 2018), drawing on studies that report differences in strategy use between male and female learners. Oxford et al. (1988) conducted one of the first systematic examinations of gender differences in LLS, reviewing the few studies available at the time. They concluded that women tended to use a broader and more frequent range of strategies. Subsequent studies have generally corroborated this pattern. Ehrman and Oxford (1995) found that professional adult women learning languages other than English in the US used more strategies than men. Green and Oxford (1995) similarly reported that female university students from Puerto Rico employed a broader range of social, affective, and metacognitive strategies. Pawlak (2013) observed that Polish female English majors reported significantly higher overall use of LLS, especially in memory and metacognitive categories. Montero-SaizAja (2021) also reported that female teenagers used significantly more strategies overall, although no differences were found in productive vocabulary. More recently, Chen and Zhang (2024) found no gender differences in overall strategy use among adults, but women still reported significantly

more frequent use of memory and affective strategies, suggesting that any female advantage may be limited to particular strategy categories.

Although some studies have also reported no gender differences in LLS use (Abuzaid & Griffiths, 2024; Risueño Martínez et al., 2016), the literature suggests a general trend of female learners reporting broader and more frequent LLS use than male learners. However, additional variables may be moderating the relationship between gender and LLS use. This study explores the potential interaction of gender and CLIL in the use of learning strategies and tactics for pronunciation learning and improvement among young learners.

3. The Present Study

Previous research seems to indicate that female learners use LLS more frequently and in greater variety. However, gender differences remain uncertain for strategies focused on learning and improving pronunciation. Moreover, existing studies tend to focus on adult learners, leaving gender-related dynamics among younger learners underexplored. This study compares the use of pronunciation learning strategies (PLS) and pronunciation learning tactics (PLT) by gender between young CLIL and non-CLIL samples. To this end, the following research questions are posed:

RQ1: Are there differences in the frequency of self-reported PLS use between young boys and girls in CLIL and non-CLIL contexts?

RQ2: Are there differences in the frequency of self-reported PLT use between young boys and girls in CLIL and non-CLIL contexts?

4. Methodology

4.1. Participants

A total of 327 English learners participated in this study (163 boys and 164 girls). The participants were in grades 3 and 4, ranging in age from 7 to 10 years. They were recruited from five state-funded primary schools located in a monolingual region in northern Spain. Three of these schools followed a CLIL approach, incorporating English both through EFL lessons and content-based instruction in non-linguistic subjects such as Arts and Crafts, Music, and Science. The remaining two schools followed a traditional approach where English was taught solely through the EFL subject. Within the CLIL sample, there were 90 boys and 88 girls; in the non-CLIL sample, 73 boys and 76 girls. Although the

biographical questionnaire allowed for other gender identities, all participants identified as either boys or girls.

The amount of English exposure varied based on instructional approach and grade, in line with regional educational regulations. By the time of data collection, Grade 3 CLIL learners had received a minimum of 434 hours of English instruction, compared to 638 hours for Grade 4. In contrast, non-CLIL Grade 3 and Grade 4 learners had received at least 249 and 379 hours, respectively. Notably, Grade 3 CLIL learners had accumulated more instructional hours than Grade 4 non-CLIL learners, underscoring the greater overall English exposure inherent in the CLIL approach.

4.2. Instruments

The study employed a 27-item questionnaire in Spanish using a 5-point Likert scale to examine learners' self-reported use of PLS and PLT. The instrument was adapted from Oxford's (1990) SILL, focusing on items more directly related to pronunciation. Prior to data collection, a pilot version of the questionnaire was administered to a small group of learners to ensure clarity and age appropriateness. The tactics from the questionnaire corresponded to five different types of PLS: cognitive, memory, metacognitive, affective, and social. Although Oxford's taxonomy (1990) was used, compensatory strategies were excluded from the study. This decision was made because such strategies may have limited practical relevance in pronunciation learning (Pawlak, 2013), a view supported by the scarcity of such tactics in the literature, with proximal articulation being one of the few examples described (Peterson, 2000). Proximal articulation is generally assumed to occur spontaneously and unconsciously among L2 learners rather than being the result of conscious, deliberate strategy use. For this reason, the study focuses on more practical, conscious, and teachable strategies and tactics.

Internal consistency measures like Cronbach's alpha were not calculated for the PLS categories. This decision reflects the recognition that tactics grouped by function may not necessarily demonstrate internal homogeneity. Prior research (Całka, 2011; Pawlak, 2010; Szyszka, 2017) showed that learners' use of tactics within the same PLS category could vary significantly. Such variability suggests that computing internal reliability metrics might yield artificially low or misleading results, given the heterogeneous nature of PLS use.

Although scholars argue for the inclusion of additional data sources (triangulation) in questionnaire-based research (Pawlak & Szyszka, 2018), this study could not employ additional research methods. Family consent restrictions limited the use of additional qualitative methods such as interviews or observations. An open-ended item invited learners to report any additional strategies not listed, but responses were sparse and overlapped with those already covered by the close-ended section. Since the study explores gender differences in strategy use rather than identifying strategies and tactics used by young learners, the reliance on a closed-ended format was deemed appropriate.

4.3. Data analysis

Descriptive and inferential statistics were used to compare PLS and PLT use by gender across contexts. Items were grouped into PLS categories (cognitive, memory, metacognitive, affective, and social), and an overall score was computed to represent general strategy use. Because the variables met normality assumptions, as indicated by the Kolmogorov–Smirnov test results ($p > .05$) and by visual inspection of histograms, parametric tests were used. An independent-samples t-test was used to compare the mean scores of PLS categories between boys and girls with significance set at $p < .05$. Effect sizes were calculated using Cohen's d and interpreted according to conventional thresholds: small ($d = 0.20$), medium ($d = 0.50$), and large ($d = 0.80$). Comparisons were conducted within the CLIL and non-CLIL subsamples to explore possible interactions between gender and instructional context.

An item-by-item comparison was also conducted to reveal differences in tactics that might not emerge from the broader PLS analysis. Each questionnaire item, corresponding to a different PLT, was analyzed comparing boys and girls within the CLIL and non-CLIL subsamples. As item responses were ordinal, derived from a Likert scale, non-parametric statistics were applied. The Mann-Whitney U test was used for group comparisons, with significance set at $p < .05$. Effect sizes were calculated using rank-biserial correlation (r), interpreted following common benchmarks: small ($r = .10$), medium ($r = .30$), and large ($r = .50$). Medians were used as the primary measure of central tendency, since means and standard deviations were not appropriate indicators for this type of data. However, when significant differences emerged despite identical medians, means were additionally reported for interpretive clarity.

5. Results

This section presents the results of the PLS and PLT analyses addressing the research questions. The first research question concerns the comparison of PLS use by gender in both CLIL and non-CLIL instructional contexts. Table 1 summarizes the descriptive and inferential statistics. Across both genders and instructional contexts, the use of PLS ranged from low to moderate, with mean scores between 2 and 3 on a five-point scale. This pattern was consistent across cognitive, memory, affective, and social strategies. Metacognitive PLS stood out as the only category with mean scores exceeding 3 in all groups except non-CLIL girls, whose score was just below that mark. The results suggest that both boys and girls use PLS relatively infrequently overall, even though they report moderate use of strategies for managing and monitoring their pronunciation learning. No statistically significant gender differences emerged in any PLS category, and all effect sizes were small or very small, except for metacognitive strategies among non-CLIL learners, where the effect size approached small-to-medium ($d = 0.285$). The findings suggest broadly similar PLS use across gender and context among young learners. However, a more detailed analysis of the specific tactics is necessary to confirm the apparent absence of gender-related differences.

Table 1. *PLS comparison between boys and girls in CLIL and non-CLIL samples*

PLS	Gender	CLIL				Non-CLIL			
		Mean (SD)	t	p	d	Mean (SD)	t	p	d
Cognitive	Boys	2.43 (1.00)	-0.052	0.958	-0.007	2.45 (0.97)	0.865	0.388	0.141
	Girls	2.44 (0.80)				2.32 (0.89)			
Memory	Boys	2.72 (0.92)	-0.379	0.705	-0.056	2.90 (0.86)	-0.192	0.848	0.031
	Girls	2.77 (0.92)				2.92 (0.91)			
Metacognitive	Boys	3.10 (0.72)	0.137	0.891	-0.020	3.21 (0.87)	1.740	0.084	0.285
	Girls	3.08 (0.78)				2.97 (0.82)			
Affective	Boys	2.88 (0.87)	0.333	0.739	-0.049	2.94 (0.79)	0.678	0.500	0.110
	Girls	2.84 (0.86)				2.85 (0.77)			
Social	Boys	2.53 (0.80)	-0.798	0.425	-0.119	2.60 (0.84)	0.905	0.367	0.148
	Girls	2.63 (0.80)				2.47 (0.89)			
Overall	Boys	2.76 (0.66)	-0.300	0.764	-0.045	2.86 (0.69)	1.179	0.240	0.193
	Girls	2.79 (0.62)				2.73 (0.62)			

The second research question concerned gender differences in PLT use within the CLIL and non-CLIL samples. Given the number of questionnaire items, results are organized by PLS type. Each table includes the English version of the items along with descriptive and inferential statistics. As shown in Table 2, there were no statistically significant gender differences for any cognitive tactics in either instructional context. Overall PLT

use was low, indicating that learners rarely engaged in actions such as writing words as they sound or consulting a dictionary and only moderately engaged in reflective activities such as looking for pronunciation rules or noticing differences between Spanish and English sounds. The pattern was consistent across genders and suggests limited reliance on cognitive tactics, regardless of the type of instruction.

Table 2. *Cognitive PLT comparison between boys and girls in CLIL and non-CLIL samples*

Tactic	Gender	CLIL				Non-CLIL			
		Median	U	p	r	Median	U	p	r
<i>I write the English words the way they sound (eye: ai)</i>	Boys	1	3731	0.468	0.057	1	2545	0.352	0.082
	Girls	1				2			
<i>I use a dictionary to look up the pronunciation of words</i>	Boys	1	3578	0.220	0.096	1	2765	0.970	0.003
	Girls	1				1			
<i>I look for pronunciation rules in English</i>	Boys	3	3800	0.633	0.040	3	2314	0.072	0.165
	Girls	3				2			
<i>I look for differences between Spanish and English sounds</i>	Boys	3	3755	0.539	0.051	3	2490	0.264	0.102
	Girls	3				3			

The comparison of memory tactics in Table 3 likewise revealed no significant gender differences among CLIL and non-CLIL samples. In this case, a more varied pattern of results was observed, with median scores ranging from 1 to 4. Repetition-based tactics (silent repetition, repeating difficult words, repeating pronunciation from media, and repeating teachers' pronunciation) were the most frequent, while creative or embodied tactics (using rhymes or gestures) were seldom used. Overall, the findings indicate that boys and girls use memory tactics in broadly similar ways across instructional contexts. Both samples seem to prioritize repetition-based strategies, while the use of more creative or embodied strategies such as rhymes or gestures remains minimal.

Table 3. *Memory PLT comparison between boys and girls in CLIL and non-CLIL samples*

Tactic	Gender	CLIL				Non-CLIL			
		Median	U	p	r	Median	U	p	r
<i>I use rhymes to remember the pronunciation of new English words (cake and make)</i>	Boys	1	3719	0.437	0.060	1	2691	0.729	0.029
	Girls	1				1			
<i>I say the English words to myself in silence to learn how to pronounce them</i>	Boys	4	3644	0.341	0.079	4	2714	0.813	0.021
	Girls	4				4			
<i>I listen and repeat difficult words in English to learn how to pronounce them</i>	Boys	4	3533	0.201	0.107	4	2363	0.103	0.148
	Girls	4				4			
	Boys	1	3792	0.547	0.042	1	2671	0.647	0.037

<i>I use gestures to remember new English sounds</i>	Girls	1				1			
<i>I repeat the pronunciation of English in songs, films, series or cartoons</i>	Boys	3				2			
	Girls	3	3594	0.272	0.092	3	2423	0.165	0.126
<i>I repeat my teachers' pronunciation in English</i>	Boys	3				3			
	Girls	3	3763	0.558	0.049	3.5	2770	0.988	0.001

As shown in Table 4, metacognitive tactics were generally used at moderate levels across genders and instructional contexts. Both boys and girls reported high use of noticing their own pronunciation mistakes and paying attention to how others pronounce words, with medians of 4 in all cases. Other tactics, such as reflecting on pronunciation progress, finding ways to apply pronunciation skills, and trying to become a better pronunciation learner, were reported to be used from moderate to frequent levels, with median values ranging from 3 to 4. Seeking people to practice pronunciation showed modest use, with medians between 2 and 3. No significant gender differences were found for any of the previous tactics. The only tactic showing a significant gender difference was recording one's own voice, which was the least used overall, with a median of 1 among both CLIL and non-CLIL learners. In the non-CLIL sample, however, boys ($M = 1.83$) reported slightly higher use of this tactic than girls ($M = 1.40$), a difference that reached statistical significance ($p = 0.018$) with a small effect size ($r = 0.172$). Overall, learners in both contexts showed similar moderate to frequent engagement in metacognitive tactics, with gender variation limited to one tactic.

Table 4. *Metacognitive PLT comparison between boys and girls in CLIL and non-CLIL samples*

Tactic	Gender	CLIL				Non-CLIL			
		Median	U	p	r	Median	U	p	r
<i>I think about my progress in learning English pronunciation</i>	Boys	3				3			
	Girls	3	3594	0.275	0.092	3	2581	0.452	0.069
<i>I try to find out how to be a better learner of English pronunciation</i>	Boys	3.5				4			
	Girls	4	3927	0.923	0.008	3	2326	0.081	0.161
<i>I try to find as many ways as I can to use my English pronunciation</i>	Boys	3				4			
	Girls	3	3729	0.491	0.058	4	2670	0.685	0.037
<i>I try to notice my English pronunciation mistakes and use that information to help me do better</i>	Boys	4				4			
	Girls	4	3862	0.765	0.024	4	2638	0.590	0.049
	Boys	4	3655	0.353	0.077	4	2707	0.787	0.024

<i>I pay attention to the pronunciation when someone is speaking English</i>	Girls	4				4			
<i>I record my voice to see if my pronunciation improves</i>	Boys	1	3524	0.094	0.110	1	2297	0.018	0.172
	Girls	1				1			
<i>I look for people I can talk to in English to practice my pronunciation</i>	Boys	3	3791	0.613	0.042	3	2625	0.560	0.053
	Girls	2				2			

As shown in Table 5, affective tactics showed no statistically significant gender differences across instructional contexts. The reported use of PLT varied across tactics from infrequent to frequent. Across both CLIL and non-CLIL groups, the most frequently used tactics were relaxing before speaking and encouraging oneself to speak despite the fear of making mistakes, both with median scores ranging from 3 to 4 for boys and girls. They were followed by noticing feelings of nervousness and discussing these feelings with someone, which showed moderate use. Rewarding oneself after good pronunciation performance was the least frequent tactic, with a median of 1 among CLIL boys and girls and non-CLIL girls. A median of 2 was obtained for non-CLIL boys. The non-CLIL comparison for self-reward approached significance ($p = 0.059$) with a small-to-medium effect ($r = 0.162$). Overall, learners in both contexts reported using affective tactics that help manage anxiety and build confidence more often than those focused on self-reward or emotional sharing.

Table 5. *Affective PLT comparison between boys and girls in CLIL and non-CLIL samples*

Tactic	Gender	CLIL				Non-CLIL			
		Median	U	p	r	Median	U	p	r
<i>I try to relax whenever I feel afraid due to my pronunciation</i>	Boys	4				4			
	Girls	3	3674	0.393	0.072	4	2728	0.858	0.016
<i>I encourage myself to speak even when I am afraid of making a pronunciation mistake</i>	Boys	4				4			
	Girls	4	3915	0.893	0.011	4	2469	0.225	0.110
<i>I give myself a reward or treat when I do well in English pronunciation</i>	Boys	1				2			
	Girls	1	3833	0.685	0.032	1	2322	0.059	0.162
<i>I try to notice if I am tense or nervous because of the English pronunciation</i>	Boys	2				3			
	Girls	3	3874	0.798	0.021	3	2547	0.376	0.082
<i>I talk to someone else about how I feel when I learn English pronunciation</i>	Boys	3				3			
	Girls	2	3921	0.908	0.009	2	2468	0.228	0.110

Finally, Table 6 presents the results for social PLT. The results indicate low to moderate use of these tactics across samples. The most frequently used social PLT was asking teachers to repeat or slow down if their pronunciation was unclear, with median scores of 3 for both genders in CLIL and non-CLIL. This was the only tactic showing a statistically significant gender difference, found in the non-CLIL group, where boys reported slightly higher use than girls ($p = 0.043$) with a small effect size ($r = 0.186$). Other teacher and family-related tactics, such as asking for correction or requesting help from family members, as well as peer-based tactics like practicing pronunciation with peers or asking peers for help, were used infrequently and showed no significant gender differences. The findings suggest that social PLT were used sparingly by both genders, with minimal gender variation across types of instruction.

Table 6. *Social PLT comparison between boys and girls in CLIL and non-CLIL samples*

Tactic	Gender	CLIL				Non-CLIL			
		Median	U	p	r	Median	U	p	r
<i>I ask my teacher to repeat or slow down if I do not understand their pronunciation</i>	Boys	3				3			
	Girls	3	3791	0.615	0.042	3	2257	0.043	0.186
<i>I ask my teacher to correct my English pronunciation</i>	Boys	2				2			
	Girls	2	3861	0.765	0.025	1	2646	0.604	0.046
<i>I practice English pronunciation with my peers</i>	Boys	1				2			
	Girls	2	3580	0.232	0.095	2	2452	0.202	0.116
<i>I ask my family for help with English pronunciation</i>	Boys	3				4			
	Girls	3	3830	0.700	0.032	3	2381	0.127	0.141
<i>I ask my peers for help with English pronunciation</i>	Boys	2				2			
	Girls	2	3632	0.321	0.082	1.5	2672	0.680	0.036

6. Discussion

The current study investigated whether gender influences young learners' use of pronunciation learning strategies and tactics in CLIL and non-CLIL contexts. To this end, two research questions were formulated. The first concerned possible gender-based differences in the use of overall, cognitive, memory, metacognitive, affective and social PLS within CLIL and non-CLIL groups. The results revealed no statistically significant gender differences in either instructional context, with effect sizes that were either negligible or small. The only exception was the comparison of metacognitive PLS use among non-CLIL learners, where the magnitude of difference between boys and girls was between small and medium.

The findings suggest that gender may not be a determining variable in the frequency of PLS use among young learners, irrespective of the type of instruction received. This could be interpreted as a sign that gender, as a social construct, may not yet exert a strong influence on children's learning behavior. However, while the interaction between gender and age may be responsible for the lack of differences between boys and girls, this outcome seems to be consistent with the findings of Rokoszewska (2014), who also reported no significant gender differences for any type of PLS among an older sample of university students. Although this may indicate a general trend suggesting that gender does not influence strategy use for pronunciation learning, one study reports a different outcome. Pawlak (2018) found that female participants reported more frequent use of PLS in an English major context. However, the author acknowledged that a gender imbalance in the sample may have contributed to these findings (p. 201).

In light of numerous studies reporting that female learners tend to use a greater number of general strategies aimed at improving overall language proficiency (Ehrman & Oxford, 1989; Green & Oxford, 1995; Pawlak, 2013; Montero-SaizAja, 2021; Chen & Zhang, 2024), the present findings suggest that while gender may influence broader language learning strategy use, it might not necessarily affect strategies specifically targeting pronunciation. One possible explanation for this is the overall low frequency of PLS reported by the participants in this study. If pronunciation-focused strategies are infrequently employed across the board, gender-based variation in their use may not emerge. It follows that further research is necessary to explore gender as a variable in contexts where learners possess higher pronunciation awareness, to determine whether gender-related patterns in PLS use arise under such conditions.

While broader studies on CLIL and gender suggest that CLIL may mitigate gender differences observed in non-CLIL contexts (Gallardo-del-Puerto & Blanco-Suárez, 2021; Heras & Lasagabaster, 2015; Nieto Moreno de Diezmas & Hill, 2019), other findings reveal either a similar absence of gender differences in non-CLIL contexts (Doiz et al., 2014; Martínez Agudo, 2022) or the persistence of gender effects even in CLIL environments (Lasagabaster, 2008; Roquet et al., 2016). These inconclusive results may indicate that CLIL moderates the relationship between gender and learning outcomes differently depending on the specific variable under investigation. Regarding strategy use, existing research has shown that boys and girls tend to use LLS (Milla & Gutierrez-Mangado, 2019) and compensatory strategies (Basterrechea et al., 2017) with comparable

frequency in CLIL contexts. However, these studies did not include non-CLIL control groups, making it difficult to ascertain whether the absence of differences is attributable to CLIL instruction itself. Therefore, additional comparative studies involving both CLIL and non-CLIL learners are needed, particularly in relation to strategy use, in order to determine the extent to which CLIL moderates gender differences. At present, the findings of this study suggest that CLIL does not influence gender-related differences in PLS use, given that similar results were observed in both instructional contexts. Nonetheless, longitudinal research is needed to investigate whether such differences might emerge over time as learners progress in age and receive increased exposure to English instruction.

The second research question of the present study focused on the comparison of specific PLT to determine whether certain tactics are used differently by boys and girls. The results of these comparisons revealed that, overall, both genders report using tactics aimed at learning and improving L2 pronunciation in similar ways, regardless of instructional context (CLIL or non-CLIL). However, two tactics showed statistically significant gender differences, and one additional tactic approached significance in the non-CLIL sample. Specifically, non-CLIL boys reported recording themselves, rewarding good pronunciation performance, and asking teachers to repeat or slow down more frequently than girls. These findings contrast with previous research involving adult learners, in which Polish female students reported significantly higher use of tactics such as self-reward and asking interlocutors to repeat or slow down (Pawlak, 2013). However, as noted earlier, the gender imbalance in Pawlak's (2013) study, combined with the fact that the participants were Polish university students majoring in English, may limit the comparability of the two samples. It is also worth noting that the tactics under investigation differed in focus. In the current study, all tactics relate specifically to pronunciation, while Pawlak's study examined strategy use in L2 learning more broadly, without focusing on a particular skill area.

The significant differences found in the non-CLIL sample should not be interpreted as conclusive evidence of gender-related differences in that group. Only two tactics reached significance, and one approached it, representing a small subset of the 27 tactics analyzed. Additionally, effect size coefficients for these comparisons were small. This further suggests that the practical relevance of the findings is limited. Moreover, both boys and girls reported using these tactics infrequently, which further limits the interpretive value of the differences and suggests that these behaviors may not be central to learners'

pronunciation learning habits at this stage. This resonates with Pawlak's (2013) claim that gender-related variation in strategy use tends to be restricted to specific tactics and does not generalize across entire categories.

The variability in frequency of tactics within the same strategy function (cognitive, memory, metacognitive, affective and social) is consistent with earlier findings in PLS that have shown that learners prioritize selected tactics within each strategy type rather than consistently favoring all tactics belonging to a given category (Całka, 2011; Pawlak, 2010; Szyszka, 2017). For research purposes, this trend supports the need for instruments that include a broad range of tactics, a need already recognized in the literature (Pawlak, 2010). Questionnaires with a limited number of items may provide less reliable data, as learners tend to report varying levels of use even for tactics belonging to the same strategy type (Pawlak & Szyszka, 2018).

Taken together, the findings of the present study can be interpreted in two main ways. First, gender might not yet exert a strong influence on learning behaviors at this early developmental stage. Alternatively, gender may be a weak or non-relevant predictor of pronunciation learning strategies and tactics regardless of age, suggesting that other variables play a more decisive role in shaping PLS and PLT use. Further empirical evidence is needed to clarify the role of gender among young learners in language learning strategies and other learning variables, as well as its influence on PLS compared with other skill-specific LLS. The small gender differences observed in the non-CLIL sample, which were not present in the CLIL group, also warrant further investigation. Additional research is required to determine whether such differences become more pronounced as learners grow older and to verify whether CLIL contexts indeed offer more equitable opportunities for boys and girls in language learning processes.

7. Conclusions

The present study investigated gender differences among young CLIL and non-CLIL learners in their self-reported frequency of using strategies and tactics aimed at developing and improving pronunciation. A questionnaire comprising 27 items, categorized into cognitive, memory, metacognitive, affective, and social PLS, was administered. The analysis of PLS use between boys and girls in each instructional context revealed no statistically significant gender differences in any of the PLS categories. The findings suggest that gender may not be a determining variable in PLS use among young learners, regardless of instructional context.

The additional analysis of the 27 individual tactics listed in the questionnaire yielded comparable results. In the CLIL group, no significant gender differences were observed. In the non-CLIL group, only two tactics showed statistically significant differences, with one additional tactic approaching significance in favor of boys; however, effect sizes were small. These outcomes contrast with previous research on broader strategy use among older learners, where female participants consistently reported more frequent and more diverse strategy use. Therefore, additional research is warranted to examine strategy use across gender and age groups, utilizing both general and skill-specific frameworks to further elucidate the role of gender.

A key limitation of this study is the reliance on a single method of data collection. As noted in the methodology section, triangulation is often recommended to enhance the validity of findings (Pawlak & Szyszka, 2018), but it was not feasible in this case. Future studies should consider incorporating additional sources of data, such as learner diaries, interviews, or focus groups, to provide a more detailed and comprehensive understanding of strategy use, particularly in relation to potential gender-based differences in pronunciation learning.

Building upon the current study's contribution, the next step will involve adopting a longitudinal design to investigate the development of gender dynamics in PLS use within both CLIL and non-CLIL contexts. Such approaches would help determine whether gender remains a non-influential factor or whether distinctions emerge over time in older learner populations. Moreover, exploring other individual learner variables, such as motivation or anxiety, could offer further insights into the strategic behavior of learners based on their individual profiles.

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References

- Abuzaid, M., & Griffiths, C. (2024). Language learning strategies, proficiency and gender: The case of Palestinian university students. *Language Teaching Research Quarterly*, *41*, 52–66. <https://doi.org/10.32038/ltrq.2024.41.05>
- Alghazo, S. (2021). Pronunciation learning strategies used by EFL university students: A classroom-based investigation. In M. Pawlak (Ed.), *Investigating individual learner differences in second language learning* (pp. 151–171). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-75726-7_7
- Baker Smemoe, W., & Haslam, N. (2013). The effect of language learning aptitude, strategy use and learning context on L2 pronunciation learning. *Applied Linguistics*, *34*(4), 435–456. <https://doi.org/10.1093/applin/ams066>
- Basterrechea, M., Martínez-Adrián, M., & Gallardo-del-Puerto, F. (2017). Gender effects on strategic competence: A survey study on compensatory strategies in a CLIL context. *ELIA: Estudios de Lingüística Inglesa Aplicada*, *17*, 47–70. <https://dx.doi.org/10.12795/elia.2017.i17.03>
- Całka, A. (2011). Pronunciation learning strategies - Identification and classification. In M. Pawlak, E. Waniek-Klimczak, & J. Majer (Eds.), *Speaking and instructed foreign language acquisition* (pp. 149–168). Multilingual Matters. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781847694126-012>
- Castellano-Risco, I. (2019). Understanding the selection of vocabulary learning strategies: The impact of the language teaching approach. *Journal of English Studies*, *17*, 75–101. <https://doi.org/10.18172/jes.3779>
- Chamot, A. U. (2005). Language learning strategy instruction: Current issues and research. *Annual Review of Applied Linguistics*, *25*, 112–130. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0267190505000061>
- Chen, R., & Zhang, L. (2024). On Chinese learning strategies of learners from Central Asian countries: An analysis of gender, age, and learning duration effects. *Frontiers in Psychology*, *15*, 1372005. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2024.1372005>
- Dalton, C., & Seidlhofer, B. (1994). *Pronunciation*. Oxford University Press.

- Dewaele, J.-M., & MacIntyre, P. D. (2014). The two faces of Janus? Anxiety and enjoyment in the foreign language classroom. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 4(2), 237–274. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssl.t.2014.4.2.5>
- Díaz-Campos, M. (2004). Context of learning in the acquisition of Spanish second language phonology. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 26(2), 249–273. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0272263104262052>
- Doiz, A., Lasagabaster, D., & Sierra, J. M. (2014). CLIL and motivation: The effect of individual and contextual variables. *The Language Learning Journal*, 42(2), 209–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2014.889508>
- Eckstein, G. T. (2007). *A correlation of pronunciation learning strategies with spontaneous English pronunciation of adult ESL learners* [Unpublished master's thesis]. Brigham Young University. <https://hdl.lib.byu.edu/1877/etd1973>
- Ehrman, M., & Oxford, R. (1989). Effects of sex differences, career choice, and psychological type on adult language learning strategies. *The Modern Language Journal*, 73(1), 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1989.tb05302.x>
- Ehrman, M. E., & Oxford, R. L. (1995). Cognition plus: Correlates of language learning success. *The Modern Language Journal*, 79(1), 67–89. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1540-4781.1995.tb05417.x>
- Gallardo-del-Puerto, F., & Blanco-Suárez, Z. (2021). Foreign language motivation in primary education students: The effects of additional CLIL and gender. *Journal of Immersion and Content-Based Language Education*, 9(1), 58–84. <https://doi.org/10.1075/jicb.19023.gal>
- Green, J. M., & Oxford, R. (1995). A closer look at learning strategies, L2 proficiency, and gender. *TESOL Quarterly*, 29(2), 261–297. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3587625>
- Griffiths, C. (2018). *The strategy factor in successful language learning: The tornado effect*. Multilingual Matters. <https://doi.org/10.21832/9781783099757>
- Heras, A., & Lasagabaster, D. (2015). The impact of CLIL on affective factors and vocabulary learning. *Language Teaching Research*, 19(1), 70–88. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168814541736>

- Iwaniec, J. (2019). Language learning motivation and gender: The case of Poland. *International Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 29(1), 130–143. <https://doi.org/10.1111/ijal.12251>
- Jarosz, A. (2021). Incidental development of pronunciation learning strategies. *Research in Language*, 19(3), 267–282. <https://doi.org/10.18778/1731-7533.19.3.03>
- Lasagabaster, D. (2008). Foreign language competence in content and language integrated courses. *The Open Applied Linguistics Journal*, 1(1), 30–41. <https://doi.org/10.2174/1874913500801010030>
- Martínez Agudo, J. de D. (2022). Do CLIL programmes help to balance out gender differences in content and language achievement? *Language, Culture and Curriculum*, 35(2), 119–133. <https://doi.org/10.1080/07908318.2021.1942033>
- Milla, R., & Gutierrez-Mangado, M. J. (2019). Language learning strategy reported choice by bilingual children in CLIL: The effect of age, proficiency and gender in L3 learners of English. *System*, 87, 102165. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2019.102165>
- Montero-SaizAja, A. (2021). Gender-based differences in EFL learners' language learning strategies and productive vocabulary. *Theory and Practice of Second Language Acquisition*, 7(2), 83–107. <https://doi.org/10.31261/TAPSLA.8594>
- Nieto Moreno de Diezmas, E., & Hill, T. M. (2019). Social science learning and gender-based differences in CLIL: A preliminary study. *ELIA: Estudios de Lingüística Inglesa Aplicada*, 19, 177–204. <https://dx.doi.org/10.12795/elia.2019.i19.08>
- Oxford, R. (1990). *Language learning strategies: What every teacher should know*. Heinle & Heinle.
- Oxford, R. (2017). *Teaching and researching language learning strategies: Self-regulation in context*. Routledge.
- Oxford, R., & Gkonou, C. (2018). Interwoven: Culture, language, and learning strategies. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 8(2), 403–426. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssllt.2018.8.2.10>
- Oxford, R., Nyikos, M., & Ehrman, M. (1988). Vive la différence? Reflections on sex differences in use of language learning strategies. *Foreign Language Annals*, 21(4), 321–329. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1944-9720.1988.tb01076.x>

- Pawlak, M. (2010). Designing and piloting a tool for the measurement of the use of pronunciation learning strategies. *Research in Language*, 8, 189–202. <https://doi.org/10.2478/v10015-010-0005-6>
- Pawlak, M. (2013). Another look at the effect of gender on the use of language learning strategies: The case of advanced Polish learners of English. In K. Piątkowska & E. Kościalkowska-Okońska (Eds.), *Correspondences and contrasts in foreign language pedagogy and translation studies* (pp. 43–58). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-00161-6_4
- Pawlak, M. (2018). The use of pronunciation learning strategies in form-focused and meaning-focused activities as a function of contextual and individual variables. In R. Oxford & C. Amerstorfer (Eds.), *Language learning strategies and individual learner characteristics: Situating strategy use in diverse contexts* (pp. 187–205). Bloomsbury.
- Pawlak, M. (2021). Investigating language learning strategies: Prospects, pitfalls and challenges. *Language Teaching Research*, 25(5), 817–835. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1362168819876156>
- Pawlak, M., & Szyszka, M. (2018). Researching pronunciation learning strategies: An overview and a critical look. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 8(2), 293–323. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssllt.2018.8.2.6>
- Peterson, S. (2000). *Pronunciation learning strategies: A first look* [Unpublished research report]. ERIC. (ED 450 599)
- Risueño Martínez, J. J., Vázquez Pérez, M. L., Hidalgo Navarrete, J., & de la Blanca de la Paz, S. (2016). Language learning strategy use by Spanish EFL students: The effect of proficiency level, gender, and motivation. *Revista de Investigación Educativa*, 34(1), 133–149. <https://doi.org/10.6018/rie.34.1.232981>
- Rokoszewska, K. (2012). The influence of pronunciation learning strategies on mastering English vowels. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 2(3), 391–413. <https://doi.org/10.14746/ssllt.2012.2.3.7>
- Rokoszewska, K. (2014). The influence of pronunciation learning strategies on the perception and production of English monothongs and diphthongs – Gender differences. In P. Sznurkowski, E. Pawlikowska-Asendrych, & B. Rusek (Eds.),

Porozumienie i dialog na płaszczyźnie wielokulturowej (pp. 199–212).
Wydawnictwo im. Stanisława Podobińskiego Akademii im. Jana Długosza w
Częstochowie.

- Roquet, H., Llopis, J., & Pérez-Vidal, C. (2016). Does gender have an impact on the potential benefits learners may achieve in two contexts compared: Formal instruction and formal instruction + content and language integrated learning? *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, 19(4), 370–386. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13670050.2014.992389>
- Rubin, J. (1975). What the ‘good language learner’ can teach us. *TESOL Quarterly*, 9(1), 41–51. <https://doi.org/10.2307/3586011>
- Sardegna, V. G. (2022). Evidence in favor of a strategy-based model for English pronunciation instruction. *Language Teaching*, 55(3), 363–378. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0261444821000380>
- Szyska, M. (2014). Pronunciation learning strategy chains: A qualitative approach. In D. Gabryś-Barker & A. Wojtaszek (Eds.), *Studying second language acquisition from a qualitative perspective* (pp. 35–47). Springer International Publishing. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-08353-7_3
- Szyska, M. (2017). *Pronunciation learning strategies and language anxiety: In search of an interplay*. Springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-50642-5>